

LEADING TYPES OF ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. METHODS OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The preschool age period is important in the life of a child. During this period, the child has a high level of cognitive activity, has a well-developed ability to remember, has a high level of flexibility and learning. To determine the correct development of the child and his interests, it is necessary to know the leading types of activities in the life of the child in the preschool age period. This article will talk about the leading activities in preschool children, as well as ways of developing speech in them.

ВЕДУЩИЕ ВИДЫ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНИКА. МЕТОДЫ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕЧИ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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ABSTRACT

Дошкольный возраст становится важным в жизни ребенка. В этот период у ребенка на высоком уровне сформирована познавательная деятельность, хорошо развита способность к запоминанию, высокая гибкость и обучаемость. Для правильного развития ребенка и определения его интересов необходимо знать ведущие виды деятельности в жизни ребенка в дошкольный период. В данной статье речь пойдет о ведущих видах деятельности дошкольников, а также о методах развития у них речи.

The leading types of activities in preschool children are very wide and play an important role in promoting their development. The following types of activities are considered to be able to help in the development of children:

Games and toys: through games, children educate themselves physically, intellectually and socially. Further didactic games play an important role in the development of children and benefit them in various aspects.

1. *Educational Approach*. Knowledge enhancement: through didactic games, children acquire new knowledge and skills. These games help to learn knowledge related to mathematics, language, history and other sciences in an interesting and understandable way.

2. *Social Skills*. Collaboration: didactic games teach children to work together, communicate and help each other. This develops their social skills.

Queue waiting and patience: queue waiting teaches you to respect rules and be patient.

3. *Cognitive Development*. Problem solving: children develop problem solving, strategic thinking and analytical skills through didactic games.

Memory and attention: these games help to increase memory and attention, since in most cases children will have to pay attention to the rules and details.

4. *Physical Development*

Physical activity: some didactic games involve physical movements, which contribute to the overall physical development of children.

5. *Language And Speech Development*

Increase vocabulary: through didactic games, children learn new words and phrases, which increases their vocabulary.

Communication skills: during games, children communicate with each other, ask and answer questions, which develop speech and communication skills.

6. *Interest And Motivation*

Interesting Education: games interest children in the educational process and increase their motivation. For them, the learning process will be interesting and enjoyable.

Creativity: didactic games help develop creativity, as children will have the opportunity to come up with and create new things.

7. *Emotional Development*

Self-awareness: Games develop children's abilities to express and control their emotions.

Self-confidence: through achievements and successes, children increase self-confidence.

Didactic games have a wide range of benefits for the overall development of children. The learning process through these games is fun and effective, expanding children's knowledge and skills. Art and support: activities such as working with colorful materials, painting with paper, rascrasks or plasticine, creating musical works help to express their thoughts and ensure their creative development.

Sports and physical education activities: physical activities such as football, tennis, volleyball or string activities, physical development, reward sensations, interaction with the command worker, and other physical abilities can help to develop.

Lectures and activities of various events: lectures, for example, the game of age points in the theater, classes or presentations create good opportunities for learning. It helps to ensure the development of the Uzbek language, social and personal.

Economic and professional activities: Sales, Sales, Services and other professional activities for the BoLS, help to ensure physical opportunities and social development.

These types help develop students' diverse skills and abilities, and work well as factors necessary for their self-learning, self-understanding, and social mastery.

THERE ARE SEVERAL EFFECTIVE METHODS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN:

Dialogue with short sentences: to allow children to communicate with the help of small sentences to express their thoughts. For example, speech can be developed by learning words or short sentences related to their daily activities.

Games and role-playing games: games, such as dramatic role-playing games, are effective tools for children to learn to express themselves and communicate with other people, helping to develop their speech.

Additional language learning: learning additional languages for children, such as music, additional languages, or other labels, can be effective for developing their language and communication skills.

Entertainment and complementary activities: children can be a good tool to express their thoughts and communicate with other people and organize entertainment and additional activities to develop speech words, such as adras activities, consequences and mirrors.

These techniques play an expected role in the development of students' speech and communication skills and help them to express themselves, understand their own thoughts and develop their interaction.

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